

CONCEPTS AND FUNDAMENTALS OF LEADERSHIP AND LEADERSHIP IN MANAGEMENT PSYCHOLOGY

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Abstract. *This article provides specially studied information for leaders who will develop the right work in the future and record good results in management. Any management activity has a subjective basis. Before making any decision, first of all, the leader considers all the possible ways to influence the subordinates and chooses the most appropriate one depending on the situation. And despite the fact that the tasks of the leader are defined in the job description, the way of working has the imprint of the unique personality of the leader. Leader's style reflects his personal qualities, which differ slightly depending on the characteristics and needs of the team. Leader's intelligence and culture, level of professional and political training, character traits and temperament, leader's moral values, ability to be attentive to subordinates, ability to manage a team, creating an atmosphere of enthusiasm for work, intolerance and indifference have a strong influence on style. Also, the article contains the content of the definitions given by foreign and Uzbek scientists to the concepts of leader and manager, and the opinions of Eastern scholars on management policy.*

Keywords: *manager, leader, ability, management, psychology, employee, team.*

Introduction. In connection with the recognition of the policy of modernization of production and its management all over the world, in connection with the transition of all countries to the policy of managing society, especially labor teams, based on the specific principles of democracy, the attitude to management issues has also changed. In particular, in connection with the redefinition of the principles of building a free civil society in independent Uzbekistan, and the widespread adoption of humanistic policies in social spheres, there have been certain changes in the social opinion regarding leaders and managers.

Today, under the conditions of Uzbekistan, a citizen who has creative qualities, who works for the benefit of his family, makhalla, people and society, is under social protection to coordinate his activities, to create sufficient working conditions for himself. The responsible manager must, first of all, look as a caring person, and be able to instill in himself the psychology of interest in work. Being close to the people, living with their pain, and being able to imagine clearly the prospects of every work are the qualities typical of a modern leader. The experience of modern psychology shows that synthetic choice is more important in management, especially when choosing its methods.

Literature review. American researcher Linda Jewell in her book "Industrial-organizational psychology" (2001) described her unique approach to leadership, which is one of the most important socio-psychological phenomena. She tries to reveal the interpretation of this problem in our conditions, that is, the features of the manifestation of leadership qualities in conditions where there are no open fields for showing bravery and courage. In her opinion, the effectiveness of modern production is, first of all, due to increasing the role of employees and, on the contrary, decreasing, or more precisely, reducing the role of leaders. Only then it is possible to reduce redundant links in leadership. The task of the leader, i.e. the Americans imagine the leader within

the framework of the phenomenon of the manager, is to determine the ways of effective functioning of the group.[3]

According to American researchers Mans and Sims, the best leader is a "superleader". This is a person who can turn most of his employees into leaders, first of all, leaders for themselves. The main idea is that if a person can be a leader for himself first of all, if he can convey this skill or ability to others, then the time will come when the team will work independently, becomes a mechanism that does not need a person to control directly above it. This is super leadership. [5]

Interactions in groups are top-down or vice-versa, and include specific positions of group members, relationships between superiors and subordinates. In this regard, it is necessary to talk about the differences between the concepts of "leader" and "chief". B. Parigin distinguished these two concepts. [2]

Specialist I. Mahmudov in his book "Management Psychology" (2006) makes the following comments about the interpretation of the word "leader": "...In general, in the literature, the word "leader" is used with the term "leader cases of substitution are common.[7]

According to L. Staut (2002), a well-known psychologist in management psychology, leadership should be viewed not as an abstract formula, but as a way of life of real individuals. The interdependence model of leadership focuses on the analysis of each individual's goals, personal qualities, values, and, at the same time, the possibilities of leadership ability that influence his positive growth. It is considered the capital of this leadership. [4]

The study of the problem of leadership occupies a significant place in the history of psychology. The main reason for this is that the historical studies of sociology and social psychology state that the leader's role in social life, responsibility for the fate of the country, people, progress, well-being, and happy life depend to a large extent on his personality, activity, ability, and intelligence. In the teachings of our intellectual ancestors, in folk art, there is more than enough information about just and unjust kings. In the works of Abu Rayhan Beruni, in the manuscripts of Al-Farabi, there are instructive thoughts on the personal qualities of leaders (meaning those who occupy high positions), the complex and responsible tasks before them, and guidelines for the prevention and elimination of certain evils are reported. Especially in the work of patriotic poets and writers, where the understanding, wisdom, honesty, patriotism, piety, and generosity of the leader are emphasized on the basis of scientific and practical examples, generosity and greed are sharply opposed to each other in folklore. They were called to justice. The spiritual world of people who held one or another position in the state is expressed in the examples of folk wisdom. [1]

Content: It is no secret that attitudes towards many values have changed in the 21st century. Among them, views on the issues of managing human relations and people's activities in the conditions of democratic changes have also changed somewhat.

It has become a tradition to approach the art and skills of leadership from the point of view of business interests in the literature of the new era published in the field of social psychology, management principles, and management. It is known that in foreign countries, the persons in charge of management work are called "leaders", as we mentioned above. The same term is also used for a person who acts among people, has earned a reputation, stands out by his words, thoughts, actions and ability to influence others. In this sense, the President of the United States is also a leader, and a person who has gathered an informal group around him and does not have any official status is a leader for those who follow him. [5]

A leader does not have control over time, but he can use it effectively. The question facing a manager at any level is: how to organize work efficiently and achieve the best result? First of all, it is necessary to divide your working time wisely. The concept of leadership can be defined as follows:

1. As a social person, a leader is a person who combines productive forces and production resources and works effectively as a manager of its main driving force.

2. The leader first of all makes an independent decision to carry out any work. This decision determines the goal of the leader's entrepreneurial and business activities.

3. A leader is an entrepreneur who introduces a new idea, a new initiative, and new technologies into his field.

4. The work of a leader is a laborious activity based on entrepreneurship. Sometimes the effort and money spent on it can cause damage instead of temporary profit, and the institution can suffer damage instead of profit. He should be able to anticipate such situations and be ready for them, if necessary, restart his activities, find the strength to do so.

There are also factors that do not allow leaders to understand each other properly and lead to various disagreements. It is possible to indicate three most common types of such obstacles.

These are: 1) when they see each other for the first time, they consider each other superior to themselves in terms of appearance or do not like them;

2) not agreeing with the partner's important opinions in the initial communication with the partner, etc.;

3) compatibility of worldly ideas, goals and opinions, social stability or vice versa, etc.

It is very difficult to be a team leader. The team is a majority. Therefore, their thoughts, outlook, spirituality, character, and mentality are also different. The leader will have to keep an eye on their various, good and bad works, so that no work is left out of their sight. If a leader is busy only with management and his personality, if he is indifferent to monitoring the masses under his command, then this leader should be abandoned. Not being aware of the behavior of the members of one's institution leads to the division of the team into several parties. Such a leader will harm both the state and the community. There are different definitions of the person, but the following one that fully reflects this concept is relevant: "A person as a subject, a person, who can change the external world through his knowledge, feelings and relationships."

Note that this definition lists three aspects of personality:

1. Knowledge;

2. Emotion;

3. Attitude.

Feelings belonging to these three groups are aimed at a single goal, that is, changing the external world according to the needs of a person. In order to understand and manage human behavior in production conditions, it is necessary to have certain information about the nature of the individual. When a person interacts with others in an organization, he/she participates in various social groups. In this regard, it is necessary to analyze the psychological laws specific to the groups and communities of which the individual is a member.

The issue of psychological analysis of the management process, first of all, aims to improve the activity of the leader. In order to achieve this goal, it is necessary to study the requirements for the leader, the tendency to fulfill them, and the personality characteristics that prevent the successful implementation of management activities.

Qualities of a leader. Analyzing the concept of a leader's personality, it is suggested to study its characteristics in three groups:

- Biographical description;
- Ability;
- Personality traits.

The biographical aspects of the leader include his age, gender, socio-economic status and education. [6]

In his work, the leader has to face various problematic situations that he has to overcome, to find one or another way of action to solve the problem that has arisen. Individual methods of overcoming problems are formed during the period of work, and the desire to work more with problematic situations in the direction of management also develops during this period.

Speaking about the phenomenon of leadership, it is appropriate to briefly touch on leadership theories. To date, there are mainly three theories of leadership in management psychology. The first is the theory of leadership qualities or the charismatic theory. Its essence is that not everyone can be a leader, some individuals have such a set of qualities innate, and this set of qualities ensures that he becomes a leader in the group.

For example, in 1940, the American K. Baird compiled a list of 79 qualities of leadership. This list included qualities such as initiative, communication, sense of humor, self-confidence, ability to make quick and clear decisions, organization. But the error of this theory was that, firstly, it could not explain how the above qualities are manifested and how they are formed, and secondly, not a single quality was mentioned an absolute majority of times during the interviews. At the end of the study, only 5% of the qualities proposed at the beginning were recorded in the answers of most respondents. This led to the conclusion that it is not easy to create a leadership model. The second theory is the situational theory of leadership. The main idea here is that the leader is a product of the situation. Everyone has leadership qualities, but some situations serve as a favorable environment for some individuals to show themselves and become leaders. The third theory that emerged as a result of criticism of the above two theories is the synthetic theory of leadership. This theory believes that the leader is a direct product of group relations and puts forward the primary role of the group in its realization. [9]

In recent years, many scientists, including Russian social psychologists, on the basis of A. Leontev's concept of activity, believe that leadership can be determined based on the product of activity, the group's reaction to this activity, and the person who best meets the norms and social expectations accepted in the group. In addition, the theory of social expectations is now widely accepted as one of the most favorable approaches. [8]

B. Parigin differentiates these concepts of leadership and management and writes: [2]

1) the leader mainly manages the interpersonal relations in the group, while the manager manages the official relations in the same group;

2) if leadership is a phenomenon characteristic only of small groups, the rights of leadership can occur and be exercised within the framework of large groups;

3) if leadership is a spontaneous, chaotic process, leadership is a phenomenon that occurs as a result of elections based on norms and procedures developed in a goal-oriented society;

4) leadership is a temporary phenomenon compared to management, and it takes place in a longer or shorter period depending on the expectations of the group members, their moods, and the direction of activity;

5) the difference between a manager and a leader is that he has a system of punishment and incentives, which the leader does not have, and on this basis, it is possible to influence his employees;

6) the manager can issue one or another decisions, instructions and initiatives in the group at his own discretion, and the leader has many instructions, plans, norms, and orders in this direction, so that the leader may deviate from them, it is difficult to exaggerate;

7) the activity of the manager is carried out only within the framework of small groups, since the leader is a representative of this group in a wider social circle, in society, his powers are wide and the possibilities of activity are more.

Effective management is actually the most demonstrative form of social influence. In this sense, leadership is defined as a set of qualities that can be seen in the influence that a person can give first to himself and then to others.

An important quality underlying the idea of superleadership is to create an opportunity for the leader to demonstrate initiative to others. Information about the ability to show initiative and the opportunities created for it can be found in a number of scientific literatures.

At this point, it is worth noting another characteristic common to all leaders. Even so, the leader has a reputation, or a phrase that is sometimes used without translation - authority. A leader's authority is, if necessary, the ability.

Because the authority may have been officially given to him because he is in a certain position, has certain sanctions, privileges, and opportunities. The fact is that the leader's authority always implies the emotional and volitional influence of one person on another person. The worst thing is if a person's initiative is stifled, if he gets used to not setting goals for himself, he does not care not only for the people, but also for his family, loved ones, and children, and does not think about their concerns.

In the conditions of today's reforms, we know how important it is for citizens to have an independent opinion, a civil position, and initiative, even if we take into account our national and cultural traditions. That is why the demands placed on the leaders and managers of the new generation, the qualities expected from them require the stabilization of healthy human relations in society, healthy competition and mutual tolerance, demand towards oneself and colleagues at work.

Leadership capital is a set of qualities and talents that a leader needs to be able to effectively lead those around him. These are basic, refined, innate abilities and talents that are given to a person at birth. The use of the word "capital" is not accidental. In this case, "capital" refers to the attraction of resources of demonstrated ability necessary for growth.

Results: In recent years, due to the increasing attention to the human factor, the interest in the issues of management psychology has also increased. On this basis, a special branch of social psychology - management psychology - appeared. Management psychology is such a branch of psychology that studies the problems related to management activities, the psychological mechanisms of effective organization of the activities of other groups by individuals and groups of individuals, and implementation of joint activities. Management psychology interprets the relationship between the subject and the object of management during the implementation of management goals and tasks. According to experts, another group of tasks of management psychology is the formation of management methods.

It can be seen from the analysis of the literature that the issue of the subject and object of management is recognized as one of the main concepts in the science of management psychology. Experts in the field, while analyzing the management process from a socio-psychological point of view, emphasize that it is possible to imagine the manager as the subject of management, and the employee and the work team as the object. Also, in their opinion, it is necessary for the leader to organize his activities and manage himself, to understand himself not only as a subject of management, but also as an object. Therefore, professional improvement of the leader, acquisition of self-management skills become one of the main topics in organization and personnel management.

In our opinion, the word "leader" comes from the desire of a person to lead a group. The expression "leading" means that a person with certain qualities leads the group, and that the group chooses the path of the person it trusts at its own discretion. The same situation should be used in relation to the expression "leader". This characteristic of a leader is manifested in his emotional appeal, in the virtue of attracting others to himself." The leader is never alone, he is always looked at in the circle of group members, he suggests one or another action to the members of this group. Because the leader knows the psychology of the members of his group, their moods, aspirations, interests, etc., and is the most proactive among them. If it is considered within the organization, it can be determined that there are different leaders.

For example, among the members of the group, the most knowledgeable, instructive, resourceful can be intellectual leader, among the employees, the humorous, enthusiastic, cheerful, heart-seeker, able to understand others - an emotional leader, able to invite the group to work, bold, determined, strong-willed - strong-willed leaders. They appear in the same situations according to the demand of the situation and gain prestige in the minds of employees according to their qualities. There can be good and bad qualities in a leader, but when a group reaches a leader, it uncritically accepts him as a role model and therefore follows all his actions and instructions. This explains the existence of leaders among employees whose behavior does not correspond to the norms adopted by the organization, and the fact that they have an unquestioned reputation within a certain group.

The leader in the work team is distinguished primarily by his work characteristics, because he begins to stand out from others precisely because of his work. In addition, the leader, while protecting the interests of the group, can sometimes go against the system of official relations and the interests of official circles. As a result, a conflict may arise between the official leader and the unofficial leader in the team.

Modern psychological science, through its achievements, can provide sufficient information about the nature of qualities characteristic of a leader and the ways to achieve them. In this regard, we can include the characteristics of a leader into three categories:

- 1) orientation to the interests of the community,
- 2) professional skill to take on the challenge in any problem situation and to be the initiative in solving the case to the end;
- 3) feelings, emotional attraction.

Reliability of the obtained results: Psychology studies the psychological foundations of the manager's activity and on this basis solves a number of problems, such as what psychological conditions and processes should be cultivated in order to effectively organize the work of employees and make clear and correct decisions. For example, in concrete life conditions, if the

boss is conducting a meeting, through the opinions, reports, etc. of each speaker, their psychological state is determined, new work programs are developed, and according to the decisions made, each of the boss and employees one is given special scientific instructions and advice. When management psychology analyzes the work of a manager, the main focus is on whether management is suitable or not for his needs or abilities, according to which individual characteristics he was promoted to the level of a manager, what methods of management he uses to successfully carry out work, psychological impact on employees in order to show, he focuses on a number of issues, such as what influence methods he uses. Different people have different attitudes to the job of being a leader: someone is interested in the privileges of being a leader, someone prefers the rights that will be given to him, and someone likes to take on high responsibilities.

No matter how diverse a person's ideas about the functions of a leader are, in real conditions, a leader is to direct a group of people to activities based on a specific goal, to be their leader, to carry out various activities, to gain authority, for every work done and a number of qualities are required, such as taking responsibility. In particular, it is difficult for a leader to be responsible for the nature of interpersonal relationships in different groups, in many cases, for one leader, in several groups at the same time, because the unique individuality of each person who makes up those groups is the manager. The diversity of their perceptions and the presence of informal leaders in groups require the leader to have experience in working with people, as well as psychological understanding and patience. [4]

Therefore, it is appropriate to analyze the psychological content of the concepts of "leader" and "boss", which are often used side by side in scientific literature in our daily life.

Based on the above considerations, human activity in the management process is accepted as a subject of management psychology. This, in turn, includes issues such as the theoretical and historical foundations of management science, management principles, management methods, management and leadership issues in groups, leadership skills, the phenomenon of super leadership, leadership qualities, criteria for evaluating the worthiness of leadership, the tasks of leadership, and the classification of competencies specific to the manager, creates the need for socio-psychological research.

In our opinion, the term "manager" cannot fully express the psychological characteristics of a "leader". The word "leader" is used as a reference to a group, a person who influences its members and leads to a goal. Leadership is a state of a person determined by analyzing the structure of the group and the system of relations in it.

But there are a number of other aspects that represent the quality of a leader, which we cannot analyze only within the framework of the relationship system. In this interpretation, it is necessary to take into account one of the main aspects, characteristics of a leader - the ability of a person to act in accordance with the situation. Initiative, ingenuity and skill in overcoming the difficulties that arise in any problematic situation are characteristic qualities of a leader. In a difficult situation related to solving a problem, a leader is distinguished by his progress and leadership compared to others. In our opinion, in Uzbek language, these two expressions - "peshkadam" and "yetakchi" - can fully express the essence of a leader.

Conclusion: The failure of leadership can usually be explained by the lack of leadership capital or, if not, by the fact that the conditions for the leadership role are not right. Leadership capital is often underestimated. It is not always a smart, brave or initiative person who becomes a

leader. Also, leadership capital is not just innate instincts. With its name, "leadership capital" is a measurement criterion in a certain form, which can be increased to one degree or another. Leadership is a mutually independent process. It shows three main structures in interaction: the philosophical worldview of leadership, the psychology of leadership and social orientation, as a result of which these three conditions give the leader the opportunity to get others to follow him.

Thus, any leader has a reputation. Authority is such a characteristic of a person that he has the ability to influence other people both emotionally and voluntarily. Informal reputation, that is, reputation gained as a product of interpersonal relationships, is effective. Finding a way to please employees, being able to understand them in different situations, trust, and similar factors are the criteria for gaining reputation.

The sequence of the complex of feelings listed above also has its own logic. Research has shown that emotional appeal does not necessarily have to be very prominent in a leader. The average presence of this indicator in a person is enough for him to be recognized at the leadership level. However, the low level of emotional attractiveness characteristic of a person can have a negative impact on business communication and negotiations.

A leader's ability to create a positive impression on others by knowing the secrets of communication is the main tool for increasing this indicator.

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